

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MWANGI****FIRST NAME: PERIS****PROGRAM CODE: DBIO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 00%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

The 7 key concepts with page numbers in text:

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-12)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is a very competitive skill in the modern world. It provides an avenue for sharing ideas and information that can impact policies and influence decisions. It is through writing that complex opinions, theories, and even research findings are presented precisely and well-structured. Reading through the period 1-course pack has been impactful to me in matters of writing skills. I am more knowledgeable in terms of writing styles and originality of ideas. In this response paper, I will highlight five themes that stood out for me, including essay writing, punctuation, American vs British English, plagiarism, and style guide.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Academic essays are fact-oriented work, either published or unpublished (EUCLID 2021, 7). These essays usually communicate evidence-based ideas or answer specific hypotheses (EUCLID 2021, 7). Key steps in developing a good essay include starting early

to avoid rushing through, taking time to define the question and analyze the tasks involved as well as developing the initial draft plan (EUCLID 2021, 7).

Topic search should be extensive and detailed so that the resulting essay is relevant and aligned with the current issues and ideas therein well organized. Euclid outlines the essay formats having an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). Finally, the emphasis is on starting early, staying focused, and clarity of thought and ideas during the essay writing process (EUCLID 2021, 11). Seriousness and depth of the subject matter discussed in an essay are focal in engaging the readers and ultimately conveying the intended message.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

These symbols are used in English to emphasize, accentuate, and stress written speech. They indicate where expressions begin and stop and make sentences more straightforward and more understandable to the reader. Punctuation marks also aid correct reading and enhance readability. The common types of punctuation used in the English language are commas, periods, question marks, exclamation marks, apostrophes, quotation marks, brackets, parentheses, ellipses, colons, semi-colons, and hyphens, among others.

The importance of punctuation marks is evident in helping the reader understand the message and avoid confusion and overlap between sentences and words. I have learned to always use or place these marks in their proper locations to make it easier for the reader to grasp the message.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

One of the differences between American and British English is in the vocabulary. For instance, some words used in the United States of America (US) do not exist in the United Kingdom(UK) as illustrated; Barrister(US)-Solicitor(UK), Lawyer(US)-Attorney (UK), Petrol(UK)-Gasoline(US) (EUCLID 2021, 28) Another difference is in spelling. As much as most words have the exact spelling, some notable spelling patterns are preferred depending on the form of English at play—for example, plow-plow and color-color (EUCLID 2021, 25). Lastly, there are notable differences in both vowels and consonants, as well as stress and intonation (EUCLID 2021, 27).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is using sources of information without accrediting the author (EUCLID 2021, 34). it is essential to mention the source of information to avoid committing this academic offense (EUCLID 2021, 34). Among the various ways of citing the source is intext citation and listing either as footnotes or in the reference section. Usually, citing is

done as either directly quoted from the original or paraphrased. In both cases, the writer should mention the source or apply quotation marks to the copied statement.

Euclid highlights plagiarism as unethical and wrong (EUCLID 2021, 34). Anyone found with this offense should forego the honors of authoring (EUCLID 2021, 34)

I have learned that citing is critical when an author has quoted, paraphrased, or used data or visuals from another source(EUCLID 2021, 34). Interestingly, this offense can be committed unknowingly by improper paraphrasing. Hence, scholars need to be keen and cite appropriately.

6) WRITING STYLE GUIDE

Euclid describes a style guide as a consistent documenting approach by a writer considering certain elements (EUCLID 2021, 41). Style guides are applied primarily in professional writing, such as journalism (EUCLID 2021, 41). The recommended style by Euclid is Turabian (EUCLID 2021, 41). Additionally, this institution prefers American English, though British English can apply (EUCLID 2021, 41). Professional institutions develop guidelines to aid those interested in contributing to such articles. The beauty of the guideline is that the ideas can come from many different sources, but the general outlook remains in line with that company's style. Having a niche style provides one with cutting-edge outputs and uniqueness. Readers are also attracted to specific perspectives hence maintaining of audience.

7) CONCLUSION

This session has been a great eye-opener to my writing skills. It has been very enriching to read the ACA-401D period one course pack. The videos are very informative, and I will refer to them often until I master the content style. Learning the session made me appreciate English with a renewed perspective as I work toward academic writing. This period 1 course pack is a resource that is foundational to my Ph.D. program and scholarly writing after that.

REFERENCE

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.